

PiEdge: An Edge-Driven PaaS Model for Network Slicing Automation

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Abstract—A recently proposed direction that is pursued by standardization organizations for 5G Network Function Virtualization (NFV) technologies at the core of next-generation networks (5G and beyond) is the adoption of “Cloud-native” design principles. These principles are catalyzed by Platform as a Service (PaaS) solutions that allow re-usability of common or dedicated Virtual Network Functions, in order to fulfill the diverse vertical requirements for network slices. PaaS solutions can also be extended to Multi-access Edge Computing environments (i.e. at the edge of the cellular network) to take advantage of predefined edge-based network functions and services and to decouple their lifecycle management from centralized, delay-introducing operations. Currently, core-to-edge coordination for end-to-end network slicing, from 5G Core Network to the edge, takes place at a very low abstraction level, leading to significant overheads that pose scalability and latency threats, especially crucial for mission-critical applications. To tackle this challenge, we describe a methodology for automating the interaction between the NFV MANO and edge platforms that encompass PaaS functions at the edge. The methodology offers benefits for 1) eliminating configuration, integration and management effort for end-to-end network slicing, and 2) the exposure of edge resources to the NFV MANO as usable platform services. We showcase the automation and management overhead benefits of our solution through experiments on an edge-based Internet of Things (IoT) use case, deployed at the 5G-VINNI Spanish 5G Facility site.

Keywords—Multi access Edge Computing, Network slice automation, Platform as a Service, Edge lifecycle management

I. INTRODUCTION

The fifth generation of mobile networks (5G) has introduced technologies that allow the optimal sharing of the mobile infrastructure as well as the available services. One pillar 5G-enabling technology is Network Function Virtualization (NFV), which allows to form end-to-end network slices as bundles of 5G network resources running on a cloud-like infrastructure. However, the presence of the 5G Core [1] as a part of the Mobile Cloud introduces communication delays that impact 5G applications, especially the ones with time-critical requirements. Moreover, the Cloud infrastructure performs a centralized management of the entire network infrastructure as well as user data processing, storage and analytics. Hence, a potential failure would lead to a compromise in the network slice functionality as well as to user data loss.

Given the low latency and reliability needs of many 5G applications, we observe a gradual shift towards edge computing paradigms and the development of mobile edge platforms [2], which reside closer to the User Equipment (UE). Such platforms provide a computational and storage layer to the 5G architecture and also enable faster response to user requests for computations, data aggregation and analytics. Edge platforms are usually deployed in Points of Presence (PoPs) within user proximity as the mobile base stations and offer functions to manage the life-cycle of edge resources. Additionally, they should contain appropriate functions and Application Program-

ming Interfaces (APIs) to interact with the NFV Management and Orchestration (MANO) platform in the Mobile Cloud as well as receive instructions for the inclusion of their resources into end-to-end slices. These instructions should be afterwards used to configure and connect the resources in an optimal manner. Current work in this direction is led by the ETSI Multi-Access Computing (MEC) Industry Specification Group (ISG) efforts to provide an set of APIs for allowing access to network and user information in the scope of edge applications [3].

Another faced challenge is that the Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) often have to allocate adequate edge computing resources in order to fulfill the requirements of their envisioned vertical services. In such scenario they have to search for available resource offerings, reserve them from the third-party provider and then purchase the selected resources. Afterwards, they also need to configure these resources as well as to integrate them in their 5G infrastructure, which requires a lot of effort and can result in a long lasting process. To tackle this challenge, the ETSI NFV ISG has proposed the Platform as a Service (PaaS) paradigm [4] as a mechanism to eliminate the need of setting up and maintaining edge resources from the MNO side. PaaS is based on Cloud computing principles [5] and allows the definition of reusable, configurable and composable platform services that can be synthesized into larger services. This allows to minimize substantially overall integration time and effort. Moreover, its use allows slice tenants or service providers to only focus on the quality and functionality of the provided functions and not the underlying NFV Infrastructure (NFVI).

In this paper we introduce a method for automating the LifeCycle Management (LCM) of network slices that are extended to mobile edge locations (i.e. base stations). The method is based on the presence of an edge entity interacting autonomously with an NFV MANO platform. Moreover, the edge entity includes PaaS resources in order to extend or complete a network slice. The presented method is applied to an IoT MEC-enabled use-case that uses a network slice formed using the resources and 5G infrastructure of the 5TONIC facility in Madrid (Spain). Specifically, this paper has the following concrete contributions:

- Definition of an edge entity for the LCM of edge resources as well as micro-service mechanisms for the automation of interactions with NFV MANO.
- Inclusion of PaaS services in end-to-end network slices and definition of interactions (APIs) with the edge entity.
- Extension of a widely used NFV MANO platform (i.e. Open Source MANO-OSM¹) for automating the interactions with the proposed edge entity.
- Application of the proposed method to a MEC-enabled

¹<https://osm.etsi.org/>

IoT use case. Improvements in time and effort for the configuration, integration and management of edge resources are presented and discussed.

The rest of the article is organized as follows. Section II provides background information on the NFV PaaS initiative and the MEC integration on network slices. Section III provides an overview of the proposed edge-driven PaaS solution and its interoperability with NFV MANO. The solution is then used in Section IV to extend the 5TONIC facility for supporting MEC-enabled IoT applications. Finally, Section V provides conclusions and some perspectives for future work.

II. BACKGROUND

A. NFV PaaS initiative

As the NFV architecture is being adapted to allow modularity and portability for the management and orchestration of Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) or Cloud-native Network Functions (CNFs), the main direction currently being standardized is the adoption of “Cloud-native” design principles in 5G networks. A catalyst for these principles is the PaaS initiative, which allows VNF reusability of services, in containerized format, in order to include resources and services in end-to-end network slices. PaaS allows to reduce effort for configuring, integrating or maintaining resources and services for 5G applications.

PaaS services are categorized into two types [4]: 1) the common services, which are generic, such as the monitoring or resource/service catalogue functionalities, as well as 2) the dedicated services, which are specifically required for certain applications or verticals such as the Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP) for IoT applications [6]. The phases of VNF instantiation using PaaS services are illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: VNF instantiation using PaaS services based on [4]

Specifically, the VNF Descriptors (VNFDs) [7] contain Virtual Deployment Unit (VDU) constructs for the deployment of VNFs as well as name references for PaaS services. Before the VNFs are instantiated, the NFV MANO architectural modules [8] replace the references with the PaaS service descriptors. Then, the PaaS services are included when the VNF is instantiated.

B. MEC integration in network slices

Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) platforms have recently received substantial attention, leading the ETSI MEC

ISG to define a MEC architectural framework for 5G networks [9]. MEC platforms (MEPs) are increasingly adopted by mobile network operators as a means to bring enterprise applications closer to the UE. Moreover, edge resources are participating in the formation of end-to-end network slices, the latter being deployed on NFVI spanning across Mobile Cloud and edge. Hence, to enable the integration of edge resources with the Mobile Cloud, we identify two main orchestration extremes:

- *Converged NFV MANO*: In this option the same NFV MANO orchestrator is employed for both Mobile Cloud and edge resources [10]. Hence, the MANO orchestrator is responsible for the configuration and lifecycle management of edge resources and services as well as their inclusion into network slices. A Virtual Infrastructure Manager (VIM) as described in ETSI NFV architecture [8] is present in each edge PoP to receive low-level instructions by the NFV MANO and to perform edge cloud management operations accordingly.
- *Interoperable edge and NFV MANO*: This option includes an edge orchestration entity for each edge PoP, in order to manage the lifecycle of edge resources [11]. The edge entity has some levels of autonomy and has to receive high level (e.g. templated), model-based requests from the NFV MANO for provisioning edge services and including them into network slices. To achieve this, edge resources are exposed to MANO as abstracted platform services.

The first option requires minimal adaptation of the existing 5G infrastructure, however its drawbacks are in management complexity and scalability, as NFV MANO has to control multiple edge PoPs and their MEPs. Additionally, there is neither autonomy on the edge PoP nor in the management of edge resources, as they are offered through a centralized control scheme. The second option, provides efficiency and scalability as well as independence from continuous edge and NFV MANO interconnection, which is instead handled on-demand. It also allows MNOs to extend edge coverage by leasing existing edge resources to their tenants. Nevertheless this option also has considerable limitations such as the lack of control from the NFV MANO side, the absence of standardized mechanisms (e.g. APIs) for allowing the interaction between edge PoPs and the NFV MANO, as well as the synchronization that should automatically take place when edge resources are modified. The presence of a standard API for the MEP to NFV MANO interaction would force each MEP to comply with it, whereas in its absence MEP platform providers have to carry out additional efforts for implementing dedicated APIs.

III. EDGE-AWARE PAAS SOLUTION

In our proposed model, we take advantage of the flexibility and management simplicity offered by PaaS, while retaining the efficiency and control granularity offered by centralized orchestration schemes. To this end, we introduce an enhanced VIM entity for edge PoPs that, in addition to managing the lifecycle of edge resources, exposes PaaS capabilities for the provisioning of edge services. We call this entity the *Edge Management Platform (EMP)*, and its architectural positioning within the NFV architecture, as well as its associated interactions are illustrated in Fig. 2. In this figure, the network slice instantiation instructions originate from the Operation Support Systems (OSS), which streamline operations to support cloud-native networks and services.

Fig. 2: Edge Management Platform and associated interactions

The newly introduced EMP entity in this figure is managing edge PoP virtualized resources (i.e., VNFs/CNFs, virtual links etc.), in an analogous way to the typical VIM managing Network Function Virtualization Infrastructure (NFVI) resources. Nevertheless, interaction of the NFV Orchestrator (NFVO) i.e. the NFV MANO or the VNF Manager (VNFM) with the EMP does not take place solely in a procedural, low-level instruction fashion, as it happens for the slice-agnostic VIM in the typical NFV MANO architecture. Instead, aside from instructions for the LCM of virtualized resources, the EMP can receive requests for the LCM of PaaS services in an abstracted manner that does not expose the internals nor the concrete infrastructural realization of these services. It is then within the management scope of EMP to translate PaaS requests to internal virtual resource provisioning and configuration, in order to address expressed PaaS requirements coming from the centralized entities. In what follows, we describe in more detail the mechanisms for the automatic inclusion of edge-based PaaS services into network slices according to our method.

A. Edge-based PaaS services

We have implemented two mechanisms for allowing the inclusion of PaaS services inside an edge PoP. Initially, common PaaS are implemented as shared CNFs that are included in multiple slices. In this case, the generic PaaS services and mechanisms within an edge PoP are shared across network slices and thus are independent from the slice lifecycle. Hence, when the slice is terminated they continue to exist in the edge PoP. This mechanism along with the interaction of PaaS with MEC applications is illustrated in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Edge PoP with shared PaaS services for multiple slices

The second mechanism is using dedicated PaaS instances, implemented by means of VNFs or CNFs and exclusively associated with network slices. Using this mechanism, the specific PaaS instances are following the lifecycle of the associated network slice, i.e. they are commissioned upon slice activation and decommissioned upon slice deactivation.

B. NFV MANO interoperability

Since NFV MANO is the orchestrator that initiates the network slice and it is usually deployed along with the 5G Core [1], we have assumed that it also initiates the requests towards the EMP platforms in each PoP. Moreover, it is also able to perform the discovery of EMP platforms and their associated resources and PaaS services. Hence, given the MEC architecture in [12], our method focuses on an implementation of the Mv1 and Mv2 interfaces, extended to support PaaS-based interactions. Specifically, Mv1 provides a reference point for the exchange of configurations between NFV MANO and the edge PoPs as well as Mv2 performs the LCM of MEC applications.

The EMP includes apart from the VIM interactions, additional ad-hoc interactions with NFV MANO (Fig. 2), including PaaS extensions and interoperability mechanisms for binding/unbinding with multiple NFV MANO platforms concurrently. Specifically, NFV MANO is being extended to handle the following interoperability scenarios with the EMP:

- 1) *EMP registration/deregistration*, where the EMP registers to NFV MANO and announces the available PaaS services. Following an active registration, the EMP can afterwards deregister from NFV MANO a part of previously registered PaaS services or completely.
- 2) *Slice instantiation/termination*, where the NFV MANO requests the instantiation of a network slice that includes PaaS services from the EMP. Following, the presence of an active network slice NFV MANO can also request from the EMP decommissioning of PaaS services.
- 3) *Slice operation*, where the NFV MANO monitors the status of services on the edge PoP and applies configuration primitives through the respective mechanisms that are provided by the EMP. Furthermore, in this scenario the EMP can also provide updates on new or modified PaaS services.

For the edge platform registration our method uses a

sequential procedure that is shown in Fig. 4 and initiated by NFV MANO. In detail, the NFV MANO is triggering the EMP registration (step 1) and, upon successful registration, a confirmation is returned as a response (step 2). Along with the confirmation a token is returned that enables an authenticated data exchange between the two entities. Afterwards, the NFV MANO can asynchronously query the edge services of the EMP (step 3) and get a response with both PaaS-based and non-PaaS-based services that are available for each edge PoP (step 4). Then, the NFV MANO can onboard the VNFs for each application (step 5) using a VNFD. Additionally, the VNFD contains VDU constructs for the deployment of VNFs as well as name references to potential PaaS services that are used (*paasName* in Fig. 4). Finally, the NFV MANO can trigger a slice instantiation that would deploy (step 6) and then activate (step 7) the corresponding MEC-based applications. During instantiation, the PaaS references are replaced by the EMP with concrete PaaS service deployments using the process that is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 4: EMP association with the NFV MANO

IV. CASE-STUDY: MEC-BASED IOT SLICING IN THE 5TONIC FACILITY

The proposed method has been tested with the creation of IoT network slices in the 5TONIC infrastructure² in Madrid, Spain. This infrastructure includes mobile base stations on which the MEC platform is deployed. The MEC platform is based on ETSI MEC 017 [12]. An overview of the technologies supported by the infrastructure is illustrated in Fig. 5.

The architecture is using an OpenNESS [11] and an OSM instance as an implementation of the MEC and NFV MANO platforms respectively. OpenNESS is a modular, microservice-oriented software that implements different edge functionalities, such as the User Plane Function (UPF) selection for UEs, UE traffic identification and steering within the UPF towards edge PoP interfaces, DNS services as well as UE mobility.

The current implementation is based on 3GPP Release 15 [13]. OpenNESS consists of a MEC controller and MEC compute nodes. The former provides the required functionality to configure one or more compute nodes as well as the MEC applications or services that are executed within those nodes, whereas the latter includes optimizations that are needed for edge application and network function deployments, and APIs for the discovery of application services.

A. EMP extensions on 5TONIC

The implemented extensions to enable the EMP functionality in the available edge PoP of the 5TONIC facility are focused on both OpenNESS and OSM. Specifically, we have applied the method of Section III to extend OpenNESS, in order to include an EMP platform module that manages the 5TONIC edge PoP. The EMP platform also includes a REST API for automating the interactions with OSM. The developed API is available as a YAML model online³. Likewise, OSM was also extended to include a new micro-service module for handling the registration of EMP platforms as well as their LCM and exchange of instructions for the configuration of edge resources. The module is using REST APIs to automate the interaction with EMP.

In particular, we have initially extended the OSM Resource Orchestrator (RO) module, that is responsible for the instantiation, termination and maintenance of each network slice. The extension allows to automate the communication with OpenNESS, in order to extend the slice in the edge PoPs as well as stores the registered EMPs in an SQL database. Moreover, through the added functionality we are able to monitor in OSM the registered EMP platforms, the users of each EMP platform and the tenants of each network slice that are using PaaS services through the EMP. Additionally, we have extended the OSM LCM module, allowing the management of the registered EMP platforms. Overall, the developed extensions allowed OSM to manage the lifecycle of edge PoPs through the support of EMP.

B. Application overview

For the considered MEC-based use-case we have focused on the sensing and actuation functionalities of IoT devices that are connected to edge PoPs. The devices are providing the collected data to the EMP that is available for each PoP. This is enabled through the use of a VNF that is configured with the EdgeX Foundry platform [14]. EdgeX Foundry also implements virtualization and interaction procedures with IoT devices. In each edge PoP we have also implemented common PaaS services, such as the resource/service catalogues but also dedicated PaaS services as the CoAP and DLMS/COSEM [15] protocols for the communication with smart meter devices. Specifically, CoAP and DLMS/COSEM are used to encode and transmit measurements from Landys and Gyr E650 meters⁴, using their embedded 5G-enabled unit.

The use-case is built on multiple applications, where each one among them was allocated 2 CPUs and 2048 bytes of RAM in OpenNESS, in order to have unified quantitative measurements for the metrics used for the use-case experiments. Specifically, the MEC-based use-case is used to evaluate the implemented EMP extensions based the five following metrics, where averaging is specified by multiple attempts.

³<https://github.com/theovas42/piedge>

⁴<https://www.landisgyr.eu/product/landisgyr-e650/>

²www.5tonic.org

Fig. 5: 5TONIC facility overview

- 1) *EMP registration/deregistration time*: Average time duration for the registration and deregistration of EMP instances to the OSM platform.
- 2) *Number of deployable MEC applications*: The total number of MEC applications that can be compiled and deployed on each OpenNESS MEC compute node for each edge PoP, which provides a quantitative measurement on the PoP scalability.
- 3) *MEC application activation/deactivation time*: The duration of the activation process for the MEC applications, during the instantiation of each network slice.
- 4) *Slice instantiation/termination time*: Average time for the instantiation of the VNFs and virtual links that are defined in the IoT slice.
- 5) *Message latency*: Average duration of the communication between OSM and each EMP entity.

C. Experiments

We have conducted measurements for the registration and deregistration of 20 EMP platforms, allocated to the same number of edge PoPs. The chosen number matches the total amount of base stations that are used to cover the user needs in an city-wide area. We have followed the automated procedure that is presented in Section III-B to register sequentially each EMP platform to OSM. Upon successful registration a JSON Web Token [16] was also returned binding OSM and the EMP platform. Between steps 1 and 2 of Fig. 4, the procedure also includes OSM-specific micro-steps, which aim in, and are used for associating network slice tenants to the EMP platform. In particular, the micro-steps focus on first retrieving the slice tenants and then associating them with the EMP. Moreover, before querying the available services in step 2, the implemented procedure includes an additional micro-step intermediate step to check the connectivity between OSM and the EMP platform. Steps 1 and 2 along with the described

micro-steps resulted in the average time duration for the registration of the 20 EMP platforms that is illustrated in Fig. 6 for metric 1. As depicted in the figure, the increase in average times was linear and followed the number of EMP platforms, however due to the slow response of OpenNESS to certain requests, there were often fluctuations in the average time.

Fig. 6: Registration results for multiple EMP platforms to OSM

Afterwards, we have tested the method's scalability, based on the number of MEC applications that can simultaneously be compiled and deployed on the MEC compute node, and measured their overall time duration. Similarly to metric 1, also for the deployment (step 6 in Fig. 4) there were additional specific OSM micro-steps that prolonged this time duration. Specifically, we have implemented an automated procedure that checks the supported MEC Compute Nodes and applications per edge PoP and then deployed the VNFs, MEC applications as well as corresponding PaaS services. We have

managed to deploy up to 20 MEC-based IoT applications on a 5TONIC edge PoP. Afterwards, we measured an average duration of 0.433 s for the compilation and deployment time in metric 2. Since the application deployment was sequential the measured time was similar for each application.

When the MEC-based applications are deployed, they also need to be activated (step 7 in Fig. 4), as their activation time contributes to the slice instantiation. The 20 applications were successfully activated with a measured time duration between 0.498 s and 0.835 s. For the slice instantiation we have measured the overall time duration between steps 6 and 7 of Fig. 4 including additional OSM-specific micro-steps. In particular, instantiation includes an additional OSM-specific micro-step between the application deployment and activation procedures, which allows to obtain the list of successfully deployed applications for each edge PoP. In Fig. 7 we illustrate the overall slice instantiation time along with the MEC application deployment time that constitutes a significant part of it. The figure depicts the scalability of our approach as it follows a linear trend.

Fig. 7: MEC application deployment-Slice instantiation times

Upon successful slice instantiation we were also able to measure message latency for the exchange of information between OSM and each EMP. Specifically, we have measured an average latency of 3.2 ms, which varied from a minimum of 1 ms to a maximum of 32 ms in the presence of connectivity delays. Additionally, there were no packet losses, which ensures communication reliability.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a novel method for exposing edge resources as platform services to the NFV Management and Orchestration (MANO) platform through the introduction of an Edge Management Platform (EMP). The platform services are based on the Network Function Virtualization (NFV) Platform as a Service (PaaS) initiative, and allow to complete network slices for different vertical applications. Moreover, the EMP presence eliminates the lifecycle management of edge resources and services for service providers and network tenants as well as provides a micro-service for automating the interactions with NFV MANO. The proposed method is demonstrated at the 5TONIC facility through the deployment of edge-based IoT applications. We experiment on quantitative metrics from the addition of the EMP platform, such as the EMP registration/deregistration, latency in the communication

with NFV MANO and slice instantiation/termination. Additionally, scalability metrics are also illustrated by focusing on the number of deployable edge applications on the facility and their activation process.

As part of our future work, we plan to extend the EMP platform usability for Business Support Services (BSS). This would provide them with visibility on the status and lifecycle of edge resources and PaaS services. Currently, the implementation is based on API-based interactions with NFV MANO for configuration and instruction exchange, whereas in a BSS scenario additional interactions on a service-oriented level should be also considered. Moreover, the considered IoT edge-based applications are only used for evaluation of the proposed method on a edge-enabled 5G testbed and not as a real application scenario that would instantiate network slices. In the latter case, the network slices have to be associated with Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) both at the network as well as the application level and this would qualify the slice according to the third generation partnership (3GPP) options specified in [13]. Additionally, the benefits of EMP coordination and PaaS service inclusion in network slices will be further quantified from the end user perspective.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 815279 (5G-VINNI). The authors would also like to thank Adrián Gallego Sánchez and David Badia Núñez for their valuable help and support in the 5TONIC facility.

REFERENCES

- [1] Stefan Rommer et al., "Chapter 3 - Architecture overview," in *5G Core Networks*. Academic Press, 2020, pp. 15 – 72.
- [2] Hu, Yun Chao et al., "Mobile edge computing—A key technology towards 5G," *ETSI white paper*, 2015.
- [3] ETSI, "Mobile Edge Computing (MEC);General principles for Mobile Edge Service APIs," 2017.
- [4] ETSI, "GR NFV-IFA 029: Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV) Release 3;Architecture;Report on the Enhancements of the NFV architecture towards "Cloud-native" and "PaaS"," 2019.
- [5] Shawish, Ahmed et al., "Cloud computing: paradigms and technologies," in *Inter-cooperative collective intelligence: Techniques and applications*. Springer, 2014, pp. 39–67.
- [6] A. Lekidis and P. Katsaros, "Model-based design of energy-efficient applications for IoT systems," in *MeTRiD - ETAPS workshop*, 2018.
- [7] ETSI, "GS NFV-SOL 001: Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV) Release 2;Protocols and Data Models; NFV descriptors based on TOSCA specification," 2020.
- [8] ETSI, "GS NFV-MAN 001: Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV);Management and Orchestration," 2014.
- [9] Sabella, Dario et al., "Mobile-edge computing architecture: The role of MEC in the Internet of Things," *IEEE Cons. Electr. Mag.*, 2016.
- [10] Sciancalepore, Vincenzo et al., "A double-tier MEC-NFV architecture: Design and optimisation," in *2016 IEEE CSCN*. IEEE, 2016, pp. 1–6.
- [11] Intel, "Edge Computing: from standard to actual infrastructure deployment and software development," 2019.
- [12] ETSI, "GR MEC 017: Mobile Edge Computing (MEC);Deployment of Mobile Edge Computing in an NFV environment," 2018.
- [13] 3GPP, "Technical Specification Group Services and System Aspects; Release 15 Description; Summary of Rel-15 Work Items," 2019.
- [14] Theodorou, Vasileios et al., "Network Slicing for Multi-tenant Edge Processing over Shared IoT Infrastructure," in *6th IEEE NetSoft*, 2020.
- [15] Sari, Alparslan et al., "Industrial Networks and IIoT: Now and Future Trends," in *Industrial IoT*. Springer, 2020.
- [16] Jones, M et al., "RFC 7519: Json Web Token (JWT)," *IETF. May*, 2015.